

Knowledge and Attitude toward Human Papillomavirus (HPV) Vaccination among Undergraduate Students in a Private University in South-South Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Human Papillomavirus (HPV) is a major cause of cervical and other anogenital and oropharyngeal cancers. Despite the availability of effective vaccines, uptake remains low in many developing countries, including Nigeria. University students represent a key target group for HPV prevention, yet their knowledge and attitudes toward HPV vaccination remain poorly understood.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional analytical study was conducted among 300 undergraduate students of Igbinedion University, Okada, Edo State. Data were collected using a pre-tested, self-administered questionnaire assessing sociodemographic characteristics, knowledge of HPV and HPV vaccination, and attitudes toward HPV vaccination. Knowledge and attitude scores were categorized using a 60% cut-off. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 27, and associations were tested using chi-square and Fisher's exact tests at a 5% significance level.

Results: Although 72.3% of respondents had heard of HPV, only 52.7% demonstrated good knowledge, and 45.3% exhibited a positive perception toward HPV vaccination. Knowledge gaps were notable regarding HPV-associated conditions, recommended vaccination age, dosage schedule, and service points. Good knowledge was significantly associated with gender ($p = 0.049$), faculty of study ($p < 0.001$), level of study

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How to Cite

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($p < 0.001$), and marital status ($p < 0.001$). Positive perception was significantly associated with age ($p < 0.001$) and faculty of study ($p = 0.019$), but not with gender or level of study.

Conclusion: Despite relatively high awareness of HPV, substantial deficiencies in knowledge and generally cautious attitudes toward HPV vaccination persist among undergraduates. Targeted health education programs and stronger involvement of health professionals within university settings are needed to improve HPV vaccine acceptance and uptake.

Keywords: Human papillomavirus; HPV vaccination; Knowledge; Attitude; Undergraduates; Nigeria

INTRODUCTION:

Human Papillomavirus (HPV) is one of the most prevalent sexually transmitted infections globally and is a major causative agent of several cancers, including cervical cancer, as well as anal, oropharyngeal, penile, vulvar, and vaginal cancers.^{1,2} Cervical cancer in particular remains a significant public health challenge, especially in low- and middle-income countries, where it contributes substantially to cancer-related morbidity and mortality among women.^{3,4} Persistent infection with high-risk HPV types, notably HPV 16 and 18, accounts for the majority of HPV-associated malignancies.^{1,5}

The development of safe and effective HPV vaccines has marked a major advancement in the prevention of HPV-related diseases. When administered before exposure to the virus, these vaccines provide long-lasting protection against high-risk HPV strains and significantly reduce the incidence of precancerous lesions and HPV-related cancers.^{6,7} The World Health Organization recommends routine HPV vaccination for adolescents and young adults, with emphasis on vaccination prior to the onset of sexual activity.⁸ Despite these recommendations, HPV vaccine uptake remains low in many developing countries, including Nigeria, due to a combination of individual, social, and systemic factors.^{9,10}

Undergraduates constitute a particularly important population for HPV prevention efforts. This group typically falls within the age range recommended for HPV vaccination and is often characterized by

increased sexual activity, making them vulnerable to HPV infection.¹¹ However, studies have shown that knowledge of HPV infection and its vaccine among undergraduates is often inadequate.^{12,13} Misconceptions about HPV transmission, limited awareness of the link between HPV and cancer, concerns about vaccine safety, and negative perceptions about vaccination have been identified as key barriers to vaccine acceptance among university students.^{14,15}

Attitude toward HPV vaccination is a critical determinant of vaccine uptake. Positive attitudes are associated with willingness to receive the vaccine, recommend it to peers, and support vaccination programs, while negative attitudes may result in hesitancy or refusal.¹⁶ Among undergraduates, attitudes toward HPV vaccination are influenced by multiple factors, including level of knowledge, perceived susceptibility to HPV infection, cultural and religious beliefs, peer influence, and access to reliable health information.¹⁷

Assessing the knowledge and attitude toward HPV vaccination among undergraduates is therefore essential for identifying gaps that may hinder vaccine acceptance and utilization. Such information is vital for the development of targeted health education interventions and university-based vaccination programs aimed at improving HPV vaccine uptake. This study seeks to evaluate the knowledge and attitude toward HPV vaccination among undergraduates, with the goal of providing evidence to inform strategies that will enhance

HPV prevention and contribute to the reduction of HPV-related cancers in the population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design and Setting

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional analytical design and was conducted at Igbinedion University Okada, a private university located in Okada, Ovia North-East Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria. The institution has seven colleges and a diverse undergraduate population, providing a suitable setting for assessing knowledge and attitudes toward Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination.

Study Population.

The study population comprised undergraduate students of Igbinedion University Okada who had spent at least one academic year in the institution (200 level and above) during the 2024/2025 academic session. Only students aged 18 years and above who provided informed consent were included.

Sampling Size and Technique.

The minimum sample size was calculated using the Cochran formula for estimating a single proportion, applying a prevalence of 26% for HPV awareness from a previous Nigerian study, a 95% confidence level, and a 5% margin of error. After adjusting for a 10% non-response rate, a final sample size of 329 respondents was obtained.

A multistage sampling technique was used. Three colleges were selected using simple random sampling, followed by random selection of one department from each selected college. Proportional allocation of the sample size was applied based on departmental student populations, and eligible respondents within each academic level were selected using systematic sampling with a predetermined sampling interval.

Data Collection Instrument and Pre-testing

Data were collected using an adapted, semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire developed from previously validated instruments. The questionnaire consisted of sections on socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge of HPV infection and vaccination, and attitudes toward HPV vaccination.

The questionnaire was pre-tested among approximately 10% of the calculated sample size at the University of Benin, Edo State, which has similar characteristics to the study setting. Findings from the pre-test were used to refine the wording, clarity, and structure of the questionnaire before the commencement of the main study.

Measurement of Knowledge and Attitude.

Knowledge of HPV vaccination was assessed using questions covering awareness, modes of transmission, vaccine availability, recommended age for vaccination, and dosage schedule. Each correct response was scored one point, and total scores were converted to percentages. Scores below 60% were categorized as poor knowledge, while scores of 60% or higher were considered good knowledge.

Attitude toward HPV vaccination was assessed using statements rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree.” Total attitude scores were converted to percentages and categorized as negative (<60%) or positive (≥60%).

Data Analysis.

Data were entered and analyzed using IBM SPSS version 27. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize socio-demographic characteristics and levels of knowledge and attitude. Associations between socio-demographic variables and knowledge or attitude toward HPV vaccination were assessed using the chi-square test, with odds ratios calculated where appropriate. Statistical significance was set at a p-value of less than 0.05.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the appropriate research ethics committee. Written informed

consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study.

RESULT:

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of students

Variable	Frequency (n = 300)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
16 – 20	123	41.0
21 – 25	141	47.0
26 – 30	36	12.0
Gender		
Male	77	25.7
Female	233	74.3
Faculty		
Pharmacy	163	54.3
Law	114	38.0
Engineering	23	7.7
Level of study		
200	31	10.3
300	89	29.7
400	51	17.0
500	129	43.0
Marital status		
Single	281	93.7
Married	8	2.7
Divorced	5	1.7

A total of 300 students participated in the study. The majority of the respondents were aged 21–25 years, accounting for 141 (47.0%), followed by those aged 16–20 years, 123 (41.0%), while only 36 (12.0%) were within the 26–30-year age group. Majority of respondents, 233 (74.3%) were female, while 77 (24.3%) were male.

More than half of the respondents were from the Faculty of Pharmacy, 163 (54.3%), while 114 (38.0%) were from the Faculty of Law, and a smaller proportion, 23 (7.7%), were from the Faculty of Engineering.

With respect to level of study, the largest proportion of respondents were in 500 level, 129 (43.0%), followed by those in 300 level, 89 (29.7%). Students in 400 level accounted for 51 (17.0%), while the least represented were those in 200 level, 31 (10.3%).

Regarding marital status, the overwhelming majority of respondents were single, 281 (93.7%). Only 8 (2.7%) were married, while 5 (1.7%) were divorced.

Table 2: Knowledge of Human Papillomavirus (HPV) and HPV vaccination among students

Variables	Frequency (n=300)	Percentage (%)
Awareness of Human papilloma virus		
Yes	217	72.3
No	83	27.7
Awareness of HPV vaccine		
Yes	164	54.7
No	136	45.3
Knowledge of HPV-associated conditions		
Cervical cancer	120	40.0
Throat cancer	24	8.0
Genital warts	14	4.7
I don't know	30	10.0
Knowledge of HPV transmission routes		
Through sexual intercourse	172	57.3
Through skin-to-skin contact	71	23.7
Through casual contact	3	1.0
I don't know	102	34.0
Knowledge of recommended HPV vaccination age		
9 - 14	91	30.3
15 - 25	61	20.3
26 - 40	5	1.7
I don't know	143	47.7
Knowledge of HPV vaccine dosage schedule		
One	15	5.0
Two	43	14.3
Three	59	19.7
I don't know	183	61.0
Knowledge of HPV vaccination service points		
Hospital	98	32.7
Health centers	92	30.7
Pharmacies	10	3.3
I don't know	156	52.0

Among the 300 respondents, awareness of Human Papillomavirus (HPV) was relatively high, with 217 respondents (72.3%) reporting that they had

heard of HPV, while 83 (27.7%) had no prior awareness. Awareness of the HPV vaccine was lower, as 164 respondents (54.7%) indicated that

they were aware of the vaccine, compared with 136 (45.3%) who were not.

Knowledge of health conditions associated with HPV was limited. Less than half of the respondents, 120 (40.0%), identified cervical cancer as an HPV-related condition. Awareness of throat cancer, 24 (8.0%), and genital warts, 14 (4.7%), was notably low, and no respondent was aware that penile cancer was HPV-related. Also, 30 respondents (10.0%) reported that they did not know any HPV-associated conditions.

Regarding transmission routes, sexual intercourse was the most commonly identified means of HPV transmission, reported by 172 respondents (57.3%). Skin-to-skin contact was identified by 71 respondents (23.7%), while only 3 (1.0%) incorrectly reported casual contact as a route of transmission. However, a substantial proportion of respondents, 102 (34.0%), indicated that they did not know how HPV is transmitted.

Knowledge of the recommended age for HPV vaccination was generally poor. Nearly half of the

respondents, 143 (47.7%), reported that they did not know the appropriate age for vaccination. About one-third, 91 respondents (30.3%), correctly identified the 9–14-year age group, while 61 (20.3%) selected 15–25 years and only 5 (1.7%) selected 26–40 years.

Awareness of the HPV vaccine dosage schedule was also low, with the majority of respondents, 183 (61.0%), indicating that they did not know the number of doses required for full protection. Among those who responded, 59 (19.7%) identified three doses, 43 (14.3%) identified two doses, and 15 (5.0%) identified one dose.

Knowledge of HPV vaccination service points was suboptimal. Hospitals were identified by 98 respondents (32.7%) and health centers by 92 (30.7%), while pharmacies were mentioned by only 10 respondents (3.3%). More than half of the respondents, 156 (52.0%), reported that they did not know where the HPV vaccine could be administered.

Figure 1: Overall level of knowledge of HPV and HPV vaccination among respondents

On the overall level of knowledge of the 300 respondents, over a half of the respondents 158 (52.7%) had a good knowledge of HPV and HPV vaccination while 142 (47.3%) had poor knowledge of HPV and HPV vaccination.

Table 3: Attitudes toward HPV vaccination

Variables	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I believe the HPV vaccine is effective	40 (13.3%)	114 (38.0%)	67 (22.3%)	60 (20.0%)	19 (6.3%)
I believe HPV vaccination is important for my health	45 (15.0%)	108 (36.0%)	63 (21.0%)	57 (19.0%)	27 (9.0%)
I believe I would receive the HPV vaccine if available	33 (11.0%)	93 (31.0%)	81 (27.0%)	67 (22.3%)	26 (8.7%)
I believe HPV vaccination should be mandatory for students	39 (13.0%)	98 (32.7%)	71 (23.7%)	62 (20.7%)	30 (10.0%)
I believe males should also receive the HPV vaccine	44 (14.7%)	99 (33.0%)	73 (24.3%)	61 (20.3%)	23 (7.7%)
I believe the HPV vaccine is safe	37 (12.3%)	100 (33.3%)	79 (26.3%)	64 (21.3%)	20 (6.7%)
I believe health professionals should promote HPV vaccination	47 (15.7%)	106 (35.3%)	61 (20.3%)	60 (20.0%)	26 (8.7%)
I believe my cultural or religious beliefs affect my HPV vaccination decision	27 (9.0%)	71 (23.7%)	90 (30.0%)	78 (26.0%)	34 (11.3%)
I believe HPV vaccination is important even without sexual activity	42 (14.0%)	89 (29.7%)	79 (26.3%)	65 (21.7%)	25 (8.3%)
I believe media and public health information on HPV vaccination is trustworthy	34 (11.3%)	84 (28.0%)	75 (25.0%)	77 (25.7%)	30 (10.0%)

Overall, respondents demonstrated mixed attitudes toward HPV vaccination. Just over half of the respondents agreed that the HPV vaccine is effective, 154 (51.3%), and that HPV vaccination is important for their health, 153 (51.0%). Support for receiving the vaccine if available was lower, with 126 respondents (42.0%) expressing agreement, while 81 (27.0%) remained neutral.

Less than half of the respondents, 137 (45.7%), supported mandatory HPV vaccination for students, whereas 92 (30.7%) disagreed. Similarly, 143 respondents (47.7%) agreed that males should also receive the HPV vaccine, while 84 (28.0%) expressed disagreement. Perceived safety of the HPV vaccine followed a comparable pattern, with 137 respondents (45.6%) agreeing and 84 (28.0%) disagreeing.

More than half of the respondents, 153 (51.0%), agreed that health professionals should play an active role in promoting HPV vaccination. The influence of cultural or religious beliefs on vaccination decisions was less pronounced, as 98 respondents (32.7%) agreed with this statement,

while 112 (37.3%) disagreed. Support for HPV vaccination regardless of sexual activity was reported by 131 respondents (43.7%), and trust in media and public health information on HPV vaccination was expressed by 118 respondents (39.3%).

Figure 2: Perception of HPV vaccination among respondents

On the overall perception of the 300 respondents, majority of the respondents 164 (54.7%) had a negative perception of HPV and HPV vaccination while 136 (45.3%) had positive perception of HPV and HPV vaccination.

Table 4: Association between sociodemographic characteristics and HPV knowledge among respondents

Variable	Good Knowledge n = 158 (%)	Poor Knowledge n = 142 (%)	Test statistic	p-value
Age (years)			4.270 ^a	0.118
16 - 20	56 (45.5)	67 (54.5)		
21 - 25	81 (57.4)	60 (42.6)		
26 - 30	21 (58.3)	15 (41.7)		
Gender			3.886 ^a	0.049
Male	29 (37.7)	48 (62.3)		
Female	54 (24.2)	169 (75.8)		
Faculty			40.601 ^a	<0.001
Pharmacy	114 (69.9)	49 (30.1)		
Law	41 (36.0)	73 (64.0)		
Engineering	3 (17.6)	14 (82.4)		
Level of study			20.089 ^a	<0.001
200	9 (29.0)	22 (71.0)		
300	36 (40.4)	53 (59.6)		
400	34 (66.7)	17 (33.3)		
500	79 (61.2)	50 (38.8)		
Marital status			19.490 ^b	<0.001
Single	150 (53.4)	131 (46.6)		
Married	8 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
Divorced	0 (0.0)	5 (100.0)		

^a *Chi-square*; ^b *Fishers exact*

Overall, 158 (52.7%) respondents had good knowledge, while 142 (47.3%) had poor knowledge.

Good knowledge was more common among those aged 26–30 years, 21 (58.3%), compared with 56 (45.5%) among those aged 16–20 years, although the association with age was not statistically significant ($p = 0.118$).

A significant association was observed with gender ($p = 0.049$), as a higher proportion of males, 29 (37.7%), had good knowledge compared with females, 54 (24.2%). Faculty of study showed a

strong association with knowledge ($p < 0.001$); Pharmacy students had the highest proportion with good knowledge, 114 (69.9%), while engineering students had the lowest, 3 (17.6%).

Good knowledge increased with level of study from 9 (29.0%) at 200 level to 79 (61.2%) at 500 level ($p < 0.001$). Marital status was also significantly associated with knowledge ($p < 0.001$), with all married respondents, 8 (100.0%), having good knowledge, while all divorced respondents, 5 (100.0%), had poor knowledge.

Table 5: Association between sociodemographic characteristics and perception of HPV vaccination among respondents

Variable	Positive perception n = 136 (%)	Negative perception n = 164 (%)	Test statistics	p-value
Age			18.522 ^a	<0.001
16 - 20	46 (37.4)	77 (62.6)		
21 - 25	62 (44.0)	79 (56.0)		
26 - 30	28 (77.8)	8 (22.2)		
Gender			0.001 ^a	>0.999
Male	35 (45.5)	42 (54.5)		
Female	101 (45.3)	122 (54.7)		
Faculty			7.940 ^a	0.019
Pharmacy	85 (52.1)	78 (47.9)		
Law	40 (35.1)	74 (64.9)		
Engineering	11 (47.8)	12 (52.2)		
Level of study			1.245 ^a	0.742
200	14 (45.2)	17 (54.8)		
300	38 (42.7)	51 (57.3)		
400	21 (41.2)	30 (58.8)		
500	63 (48.8)	66 (51.2)		
Marital status			10.390 ^b	0.112
Single	132 (47.0)	149 (53.0)		
Married	4 (50.0)	4 (50.0)		
Divorced	0 (0.0)	5 (100.0)		

^a Chi-square; ^b Fishers exact

Out of the 300 respondents, 136 (45.3%) demonstrated a positive perception, while 164 (54.7%) expressed a negative perception.

Age showed a statistically significant association with perception ($p < 0.001$), with respondents aged 26–30 years recording the highest proportion of positive perception, 28 (77.8%), compared with younger age groups.

Gender was not associated with perception ($p > 0.999$), as similar proportions of males, 35 (45.5%), and females, 101 (45.3%), exhibited positive

perception. Faculty of study was significantly associated with perception ($p = 0.019$); Pharmacy students had the highest proportion with positive perception, 85 (52.1%), whereas Law students recorded the lowest, 40 (35.1%).

Level of study was not significantly associated with perception ($p = 0.742$), with relatively comparable proportions of positive perception across all levels. Marital status also showed no significant association with perception ($p = 0.112$), although all divorced respondents, 5 (100.0%), demonstrated negative perception.

DISCUSSION:

This study evaluated the knowledge and attitudes toward Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination among undergraduates of Igbinedion University, Okada, and revealed important gaps that have implications for HPV prevention efforts within university populations. Over three-quarters of respondents in this study were female, which shows a disproportionate involvement of the female gender in HPV-related healthcare. Although awareness of HPV was relatively high, just over half of the respondents demonstrated good overall knowledge, and fewer than half expressed a positive perception toward HPV vaccination. This disparity between awareness, knowledge depth, and attitude suggests that familiarity with HPV does not necessarily translate into adequate understanding or willingness to accept vaccination.

While most respondents had heard of HPV, detailed knowledge of HPV-related diseases was limited. Less than half correctly identified cervical cancer as an HPV-associated condition, and awareness of other HPV-related cancers and genital warts was notably low. Similar findings have been reported among undergraduates in Nigeria and other low- and middle-income countries, where HPV is often perceived narrowly as a female reproductive health issue rather than a broader oncogenic virus affecting both sexes.^{18,19} The poor recognition of non-cervical HPV-associated conditions may reduce perceived personal risk, particularly among male students, thereby contributing to vaccine hesitancy.

Knowledge of HPV transmission and prevention was also suboptimal. Although sexual intercourse was commonly identified as a route of transmission, a substantial proportion of respondents were unaware of other transmission pathways or reported uncertainty, similar to findings from other studies conducted in Nigeria.^{20,21} Furthermore, nearly half of the

respondents did not know the recommended age for HPV vaccination, and more than half were unaware of the correct dosage schedule. Limited knowledge of vaccination service points further highlights structural and informational barriers to vaccine uptake. These findings emphasize that incomplete or fragmented information, rather than complete ignorance, remains a major challenge among undergraduates.

Several sociodemographic factors influenced knowledge levels. Although older students tended to have better knowledge, age was not a statistically significant determinant. Gender, however, was significantly associated with knowledge, with males demonstrating better knowledge than females. This finding contrasts with some previous studies but may reflect differences in information-seeking behavior or academic exposure within this study population.^{22,23} Faculty of study emerged as a strong predictor of knowledge, as Pharmacy students were significantly more knowledgeable than their counterparts in Law and Engineering. This is likely attributable to curricular exposure to health-related topics and reinforces the role of academic environment in shaping health knowledge. Knowledge also increased with level of study, suggesting that cumulative academic experience enhances access to health information. The association between marital status and knowledge should be interpreted cautiously due to the small number of married and divorced respondents.

Attitudes toward HPV vaccination were generally cautious, with mixed levels of acceptance. While about half of the respondents believed the vaccine is effective and important for their health, fewer expressed readiness to receive it if available. Support for mandatory vaccination and confidence in vaccine safety were also limited. These findings indicate the presence of vaccine hesitancy, which may stem from insufficient knowledge, safety

concerns, mistrust of health information sources, and low perceived susceptibility to HPV infection. The relatively high proportion of neutral responses across attitude items further suggests uncertainty rather than outright rejection, presenting an opportunity for targeted education.

Age and faculty of study were significantly associated with perception toward HPV vaccination. Older students and those in the Faculty of Pharmacy were more likely to exhibit positive perceptions, possibly due to increased maturity, better health literacy, and greater exposure to reliable medical information, similar to previous studies which showed that medically inclined respondents frequently reported higher knowledge of HPV and its management.^{24,25} In contrast, gender, level of study, and marital status were not significantly associated with perception, indicating that negative or indifferent attitudes cut across these groups. This shows the need for broad-based interventions rather than narrowly targeted campaigns.

CONCLUSION:

Although awareness of Human Papillomavirus among undergraduates of Igbinedion University was relatively high, significant gaps existed in detailed knowledge of HPV infection and vaccination, and fewer than half of the respondents demonstrated a positive perception toward HPV vaccination. Knowledge was particularly limited regarding HPV-associated conditions, vaccination schedules, and service points.

Faculty and level of study were key determinants of knowledge, while age and faculty influenced perception, with Pharmacy and senior students showing better outcomes. These findings highlight the need for targeted university-based health education and stronger involvement of health professionals to improve HPV vaccine acceptance and uptake.

Limitations:

First, the cross-sectional design limits causal inference between sociodemographic factors and HPV knowledge or perception. However, this design was appropriate for estimating prevalence and identifying associations aligned with the study objectives.

Second, the use of self-administered questionnaires may have introduced recall or social desirability bias. This was mitigated by ensuring anonymity, using a pre-tested questionnaire, and adapting items from validated instruments to enhance reliability.

Finally, some subgroups, particularly married and divorced students, were small in number, which may have affected the stability of statistical estimates in these categories. To account for this, Fisher's exact test was applied where appropriate to ensure the validity of statistical inferences.

Conflict of Interest (COI) Declaration:

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

AI Use Declaration Statement:

The authors declare that no generative AI tools were used.

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